

Supplementary Information for: Quantifying Subsurface Parameter and Transport Uncertainties Using Surrogate Modeling and Environmental Tracers

Nicholas E. Thiros^{1,*}, W. Payton Gardner¹, Marco P. Maneta¹,
and Douglas J. Brinkerhoff²

¹Department of Geosciences, University of Montana

²Department of Computer Science, University of Montana

*Email: nicholas.thiros@umontana.edu

Field Observation Data

Table 1: Field observation data will be stored in a Zenedo.org database as the file 'Field_Obs.csv'.

Pilot Point Numbering

Figure 1: Pilot point numbering scheme used in the Riverton site model. Open circles and associated number labels are pilot point locations and filled diamonds are observation well locations.

MCMC Trace Plots

Figure 2a: (left) MCMC posterior chains ($n=10$) and (right) trace plots showing sampling frequency.

Figure 2b: (left) MCMC posterior chains (n=10) and (right) trace plots showing sampling frequency.

Figure 2c: (left) MCMC posterior chains ($n=10$) and (right) trace plots showing sampling frequency.

Figure 2d: (left) MCMC posterior chains (n=10) and (right) trace plots showing sampling frequency.

MCMC Marginal Distributions

Figure 3a: Parameter posterior marginal distributions inferred using water levels and ^3H observations (blue filled curve); and water levels alone (green, dashed line with filled curve) in the calibration dataset. The orange curves represent the prior parameter distributions.

Figure 3b: Permeability pilot point parameter posterior marginal distributions inferred using water levels and ^3H observations (blue filled curve); and water levels alone (green, dashed line with filled curve) in the calibration dataset. The orange curves represent the prior parameter distributions.

MCMC Sampling Statistics

Table 2: MCMC sampler statistics for the calibration against water levels and ^3H .

Parameter	Units	Mean	Std. Dev	ess_mean	r_hat
n_{soil}	-	31.58	4.18	2070	1.01
$\log_{10}k_{\text{ss}}$	m^2	-15.04	0.88	1831	1.01
n_{ss}	-	17.38	3.19	2331	1.01
γ	-	0.12	0.05	1529	1.01
l_{wr}	m/km	1.45	0.03	2531	1.00
w_{r}	m/km	3.05	0.28	603	1.03
$\log_{10}k_0$	m^2	-11.06	1.26	2074	1.01
$\log_{10}k_1$	m^2	-10.59	1.23	1450	1.02
$\log_{10}k_2$	m^2	-9.89	0.99	1455	1.01
$\log_{10}k_3$	m^2	-10.40	0.98	2122	1.00
$\log_{10}k_4$	m^2	-9.89	1.11	1639	1.01
$\log_{10}k_5$	m^2	-12.21	0.94	1505	1.01
$\log_{10}k_6$	m^2	-9.88	1.18	1729	1.01
$\log_{10}k_7$	m^2	-10.06	0.90	1810	1.01
$\log_{10}k_8$	m^2	-12.04	0.82	1956	1.01
$\log_{10}k_9$	m^2	-12.10	0.93	1694	1.01
$\log_{10}k_{10}$	m^2	-9.91	0.92	1328	1.00
$\log_{10}k_{11}$	m^2	-11.82	0.74	2233	1.00
$\log_{10}k_{12}$	m^2	-10.67	1.23	1803	1.01
$\log_{10}k_{13}$	m^2	-12.65	0.69	2243	1.01
$\log_{10}k_{14}$	m^2	-10.13	1.09	2014	1.00
$\log_{10}k_{15}$	m^2	-9.78	0.59	1460	1.01
$\log_{10}k_{16}$	m^2	-11.66	0.96	1735	1.01
$\log_{10}k_{17}$	m^2	-11.13	0.95	1528	1.01
$\log_{10}k_{18}$	m^2	-10.48	0.95	2066	1.00
$\log_{10}k_{19}$	m^2	-9.65	0.73	2062	1.01
$\log_{10}k_{20}$	m^2	-11.47	0.86	2291	1.00
$\log_{10}k_{21}$	m^2	-10.41	1.24	1831	1.01
$\log_{10}k_{22}$	m^2	-11.57	0.79	1875	1.01
$\log_{10}k_{23}$	m^2	-10.74	0.95	2230	1.01
$\log_{10}k_{24}$	m^2	-10.70	0.71	2148	1.00